

COVID^X

Save The Date For the Back To The Healthy Future Event In Brussels

The 2-day event will showcase innovation and will gather different stakeholders from the scientific, health, technology, and investment communities.

There will be space for projects and companies to showcase their results and solutions, Matchmaking sessions with relevant stakeholders, brainstorming and round tables on lessons learnt and impact.

[Have a look](#)

How was the COVID-X Clinical Event?

Learn more about COVID-X Clinical Event and what medical experts had to say about challenges in healthcare systems and COVID Management and lessons learned in medicine.

[Check it out](#)

Learn more about the Game Changer CAPTAIN-X working with Karolinska!

Get to know more about CAPTAIN-X within the #COVIDXSuccessStories! Remote personalised care and monitoring assistant for COVID-19 patients using speech recognition and AI for patient monitoring.

Read

Our collaborators

We work with a range of parallel projects in common areas of research to maximise our impact and network reach.

[Check their News](#)

COVID-X

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